

APPLICATION

The unmarked R package: Twelve years of advances in occurrence and abundance modelling in ecology

Kenneth F. Kellner¹ |
Jerrold L. Belant¹ | Richard B. Chandler⁵

¹Department of Fisheries and Wildlife, Michigan State University, East Lansing, Michigan, USA

²U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service, National Wildlife Refuge System, Inventory and Monitoring Branch, Athens, Georgia, USA

³U.S. Geological Survey, Eastern Ecological Science Center, Laurel, Maryland, USA

⁴Swiss Ornithological Institute, Sempach, Switzerland

⁵Warnell School of Forestry and Natural Resources, University of Georgia, Athens, Georgia, USA

Correspondence

Kenneth F. Kellner
Email: kellner7@msu.edu

Present address

Adam D. Smith, American Bird Conservancy, The Plains, Virginia, USA

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Abstract

1. Species distribution models (SDMs) are widely applied to understand the processes governing spatial and temporal variation in species abundance and distribution but often do not account for measurement errors such as false negatives and false positives.
2. We describe unmarked, a package for the freely available and open-source R software that provides a complete workflow for modelling species distribution and abundance while explicitly accounting for measurement errors. Here we focus on recent advances in unmarked functionality to support multi-species, multi-state, and multi-season data, as well as support for fitting models with random effects.
3. For illustration, we present an analysis of Acadian Flycatcher *Empidonax vireescens* abundance on Roanoke River National Wildlife Refuge, North Carolina, USA, over 18 years. We found that Acadian Flycatcher abundance was initially greater in hardwood plantation habitat relative to bottomland hardwood forest along river levees but that abundance declined over time in both habitats.
4. We plan for unmarked development to keep pace with advances in hierarchical modelling in ecology, including better handling of continuous-time data from camera trap and automated recording units and integrated models for multiple data streams.

KEYWORDS

abundance, distance sampling, occupancy, occurrence, species distribution modelling

1 | INTRODUCTION

Understanding the processes governing spatial and temporal variation in species abundance and distribution is fundamental to ecology. Reliable inference requires a combination of appropriate study design and models of the data-generating processes. Studies of species distribution typically involve sampling multiple sites (locations), across a range of environmental conditions, and recording the

presence and/or abundance of a given species at each site. A broad class of models called species distribution models (SDMs) have been developed to obtain inference from such data, such as identification of environmental covariates that influence where a species occurs (Elith & Leathwick, 2009).

A very common issue with SDMs is measurement error. Some individuals or species may be recorded as absent when they are present (false negatives, Williams et al., 2002), and others may be

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recorded as present when they are absent (false positives; Royle & Link, 2006). Ignoring measurement errors can result in biased estimates of distribution and abundance, including relationships with covariates (Gu & Swihart, 2004; Kéry & Schmidt, 2008). A specialized class of hierarchical SDMs has been developed to estimate rates of false negatives and positives (MacKenzie et al., 2002; Royle & Link, 2006). Such models often require repeated samples (also called 'occasions' or 'visits') at some or all sites. Individual organisms may be marked (i.e. uniquely identifiable) so they can be tracked across the repeated samples (Williams et al., 2002), while other models accommodate unmarked organisms. Common examples include occupancy modelling for the estimation of species occurrence (MacKenzie et al., 2002), and capture-recapture (Pollock et al., 1990), N-mixture (Royle, 2004), and distance models (Buckland et al., 2001) for species abundance.

There are many freely available software packages available to fit SDMs that account for false negatives and positives. Examples of graphical user interface-based tools include MARK (White & Cooch, 2001), PRESENCE (Hines, 2006) and Distance (Thomas et al., 2010). Packages available for R (R Core Team, 2022) include Rmark (Laake, 2013), RPresence (MacKenzie & Hines, 2022), unmarked (Fiske & Chandler, 2011), spOccupancy (Doser et al., 2022) and ubms (Kellner et al., 2022). In addition to specialized software, SDMs are also commonly fit using custom models written for Bayesian Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) software such as JAGS (Plummer, 2003), NIMBLE (de Valpine et al., 2017; Goldstein et al., 2021), and Stan (Carpenter et al., 2017).

The unmarked R package supports many model types and has been used widely based on citation records. As the name suggests,

unmarked focuses on models of occurrence and abundance that do not require individually marked animals, although some of its methods are applicable to data from marked individuals. The package provides a complete analysis toolset, including formatting input data, model fitting, assessing goodness of fit, bootstrapping, model selection and generation of predictions. Package unmarked was first released in 2010 and has been cited more than 2000 times, averaging more than 250 citations per year over 2018–2022 based on a Google Scholar search in December 2022.

Since 2010, many features have been added to unmarked. First, the available models and associated tools have been greatly expanded to reflect new developments in the field. Second, many models now support the estimation of random effects. Finally, several new auxiliary tools, including power analysis, have been added. We give an overview of currently available models and associated analysis tools, describe a typical unmarked workflow, and provide an example analysis estimating the abundance of Acadian Flycatchers *Empidonax vireescens*.

2 | AVAILABLE MODELS

Models in unmarked can be divided into two categories: occupancy models (Table 1) and abundance models (Table 2). Generally, occupancy models require detection/nondetection data as input and abundance models require count data, but there are exceptions which we describe below. For brevity, we do not describe these models mathematically as this information can be found in the references provided in Table S1.

TABLE 1 Occupancy models and associated functions available in unmarked, organized by data type (left side, vertical) and time period of data collection (across the top).

Data type	Time period	
	Single-season	Multi-season/dynamic
Detection-nondetection	occu(), occuPEN()	colect()
... with false positives	occuFP()	
... for multiple species	occuMulti()	
>2 detection types	occuMS()	occuMS()
Time-to-detection	occuTTD()	occuTTD()

TABLE 2 Abundance model functions available in unmarked, organized by data type (left side, vertical) and time period of data collection (across the top).

Data type	Time period		
	Single-season	Temporary emigration	Multi-season/dynamic
Detection-nondetection	occuRN()		
Repeated counts	pcount()	gpcount()	pcountOpen()
Distance sampling	distsamp()	gdistsamp()	distsampOpen()
Double-observer or removal	multinomPois()	gmultmix()	multmixOpen()
Distance and removal	gdistremoval()	gdistremoval()	
Time-to-detection	nmixTTD()		

2.1 | Occupancy models

Detection/nondetection data distinguish two possible true states for a site, presence and absence, observations of which may be contaminated with false-negative and/or false-positive errors. When a single 'season' (e.g. 1 year) of such data for a single species is available, the single-season, single-species occupancy model can be fit using the `occu` function to account for false negatives (Table 1). Variations include `occuPEN` for fitting the model with penalized likelihood if there are issues with boundary estimates, and `occuFP` if false positives are possible. If multiple seasons of data are available, `colect` can fit a dynamic occupancy model, and if there are data for multiple species, `occuMulti` can examine species interactions (Rota et al., 2016).

`unmarked` also supports other input data types. If there are three or more possible states (e.g. absent, present without, or present with evidence of reproduction) a multi-state occupancy model can be fit with `occuMS` (MacKenzie et al., 2009). It is also possible to estimate occupancy using time-to-detection data, that is, the amount of time at a site before a given species is detected. Time-to-detection data is becoming increasingly easy to obtain with automated recording units (ARUs) and associated machine-learning software (Rhinehart et al., 2020). In `unmarked`, both single-season and dynamic time-to-detection occupancy models can be fit using the function `occuTTD`.

2.2 | Abundance models

Most abundance models in `unmarked` can be organized as pairwise combinations of sampling method and temporal structure (Table 2). The possible sampling methods include (1) repeated counts, (2) distance sampling, (3) double-observer sampling, and (4) removal sampling. The possible temporal structures are (1) single-season data; (2) multiple surveys within a single season to estimate changes in availability due to a form of 'temporary emigration' of individuals (Kendall et al., 1997) and (3) multiple seasons of data to estimate population growth, emigration and similar parameters (Dail & Madsen, 2011).

Repeated-count data allow for the estimation of detection probability and, thus, abundance using variations of the N-mixture model (Royle, 2004). The single-season version of this model can be fit with `pcount`, the temporary emigration version can be fit with `gpcount` (the *g* in this and similar functions stands for *generalized*), and the dynamic version can be fit with `pcountOpen` (Table 2). Despite the naming conventions, these functions are intended to be used for N-mixture models generally and not specifically avian point counts.

Distance sampling involves measuring the distance from a point or a transect to observed organisms and using the estimated relationship between distance and detectability to estimate detection probability (Buckland et al., 2001). `unmarked` implements variations of the hierarchical distance sampling model of Royle et al. (2004), which allows for simultaneous estimation of detection and abundance. The naming conventions for these functions follow a similar

logic: the single-season model is `distsamp`, the temporary emigration model is `gdistsamp`, and the dynamic model is `distsampOpen`.

Double-observer models (as their name suggests) require two humans to simultaneously survey a site. Detection probability is estimated using information on how many individuals were observed by both or only one of the two observers. For removal sampling, a single observer divides a survey into several discrete time periods and counts how many individuals are first observed in each time period. These two sampling methods are handled by the `multinomPois` function for single-season data, the `gmultmix` function for temporary emigration and the dynamic version is `multmixOpen`. This family of functions can be customized to accommodate a wider range of related models, including capture-recapture data from marked organisms (Chapter 7 in Kéry & Royle, 2016).

There are three additional abundance models available, which do not readily fit into the organizational structure described above (Table 2). The first is the Royle-Nichols model (`occuRN`), which exploits the functional relationship between abundance and detection probability to estimate abundance from detection/nondetection data. The second is a model that estimates abundance from time-to-detection data (`nmixTTD`). Finally, `unmarked` includes an abundance model (`gdistremoval`) which incorporates distance sampling data (as with `distsamp`) and removal sampling data (as with `multinomPois`) to estimate detection probability and availability parameters (Amundson et al., 2014).

3 | TYPICAL unmarked WORKFLOW

Below we describe a typical `unmarked` workflow divided into three parts. Additional details are available in the package vignettes (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/unmarked/vignettes/>). A summary of the workflow is found in Table 3.

3.1 | Study design and data processing

Data simulation is a powerful tool for understanding the capabilities of a model and determining if they match research goals (Chapter 4 in Kéry & Royle, 2016). `unmarked` includes the `simulate` function, which can simulate any type of dataset for which `unmarked` has a model. Simulating datasets before data collection can help researchers design a study to minimize the uncertainty in resulting parameter estimates. `unmarked` also supports power analysis using the `powerAnalysis` function, aiding researchers in the allocation of limited resources to increase the effectiveness in detecting covariate effects.

Once data are collected and read into R, they can be organized into an `unmarkedFrame` object (analogous to R's `data.frame`). `unmarkedFrames` include a site by occasion matrix of observation data, and may also include `data.frame(s)` containing covariate data and other information about the study design. `unmarkedFrames` can be subset using R's bracket (`[]`) notation, visualized with the `plot` function, and summarized with the `summary` function. Most models have

TABLE 3 A typical workflow for an unmarked analysis, and unmarked functions used in each step.

Experiment step	Relevant unmarked functions
1. Study design	simulate(), powerAnalysis()
2. Data collection	
3. Data input and organization	unmarkedFrame()
4. Define model(s)	Using R formulas
5. Fit model(s)	Model fitting functions (see Tables 1 and 2)
6. Model diagnostics	parboot(), crossVal(), residuals(), vif(), functions in AICcmodavg package
7. Model selection	modSel(), crossVal()
8. Model inference	predict(), ranef(), posteriorSamples()

their own specific type of unmarkedFrame, such as unmarkedFrame-Occu for single-season occupancy or unmarkedFrameDS for distance sampling.

3.2 | Model fitting and diagnostics

Model structure is defined using a formula-based notation similar to the one used widely in the R ecosystem (e.g. by the `lm` function; R Core Team, 2022). Given their hierarchical structure, unmarked models require two or more such formulas. For example, an occupancy model with a covariate for wind affecting detection and covariates for forest cover and elevation affecting occupancy would be `~wind ~forest+elev`. Formulas may include certain functions indicating that covariates should be transformed before analysis. For example, the modified formula `~scale(wind) ~scale(forest)+scale(elev)` indicates that each covariate should be standardized using the `scale` function to have mean 0 and standard deviation 1. Some unmarked functions (currently `occu`, `pcount`, `multinomPois`, `distsamp` and `gdistremoval`) also support estimation of random intercepts and slopes using the notation of the `lme4` package (Bates et al., 2015). For example, adding a random intercept on occupancy by site ID to the previous formula would be `~wind ~forest+elev+(1|site_id)`. The unmarkedFrame and formulas are supplied to the function corresponding to the desired model (Tables 1 and 2), and parameter estimates and standard errors for model parameters are obtained using maximum likelihood with `Rcpp` (Eddelbuettel & François, 2011), or Template Model Builder (Kristensen et al., 2016).

Diagnostic functions are available to apply to fitted models, including `vif` for calculation of variance inflation factors (Zuur et al., 2010), fitted values and residuals with the `fitted` and `residuals` functions, respectively, and parametric bootstrapping with the `parboot` function. Several specialized model goodness-of-fit tests are available in the `AICcmodavg` package (Mazerolle, 2020).

3.3 | Model selection and inference

A model selection table showing Akaike information criterion (AIC) scores, number of parameters, and model weights can be generated by applying the `modSel` function to a list of fitted models. There is limited support for model-averaged prediction with `predict` from a list of models, and more complete model averaging functionality is available via the `AICcmodavg` package (Mazerolle, 2020). Model predictive power can also be assessed and compared with cross-validation via the `crossVal` function, which supports holdout, *K*-fold, and leave-one-out cross-validation (Stone, 1977).

Once a top model has been selected, it can be used to generate estimates and 95% confidence intervals of model parameters using the `predict` function. Overdispersion-corrected prediction intervals and AIC scores for most unmarked analyses can be obtained using functions in `AICcmodavg` (Mazerolle, 2020). Species distribution maps (e.g. Sillett et al., 2012) can be generated by providing raster data to `predict`. The model can also be supplied to the `ranef` function to estimate posterior distributions of the latent parameters (e.g. occupancy state, abundance) at each sampled site using empirical Bayes methods (Carlin & Louis, 1996).

4 | APPLICATION

4.1 | Study design and data collection

We estimated population abundance from a dataset of Acadian Flycatcher point counts. The dataset consisted of 55 point count locations typically surveyed once per year during 2005–2022 on Roanoke River National Wildlife Refuge (NWR), North Carolina, USA. Sampling was conducted by a U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service employee; no permits were required. Point counts were conducted in bottomland hardwoods adjacent to river levees and in hardwood plantations. Each point count lasted 10 min, while an observer recorded the time period in which each individual bird was first observed (0–3 min, 3–5 min, 5–10 min) and the distance of each observation (<25 m or 25–50 m). We applied the combined removal-distance sampling model of Amundson et al. (2014) using the recently added `gdistremoval` function in `unmarked`.

4.2 | Simulation and power analysis

We conducted a power analysis to evaluate our ability to detect differences in abundance between habitat types and over time, to demonstrate this new functionality in `unmarked` (typically, power analysis should be done before data collection). We first generated a template unmarkedFrame which contained the study design for which we calculated power using the `simulate` function. The study design consisted of 50 point count locations, equally assigned between two habitat types (designated A and B), each surveyed once annually for 15 years.

Next, we provided the `powerAnalysis` function with the template study design and parameter values corresponding to the abundance and detection processes. We defined the parameters such that habitats A and B would have initial abundances of about 5 and 6 birds respectively, and abundance would decline about 2% per year. We set the distance-based detection parameter σ at the median distance of our point count radius (25 m) and the removal-based probability of availability at 0.27 (similar to the real data). With this information, the `powerAnalysis` function generated 100 simulated datasets and fit the removal-distance sampling model to each dataset. Finally, `powerAnalysis` calculated the proportion of datasets for which a given coefficient (e.g. for habitat differences) was statistically significant (with $\alpha=0.05$) as a measure of power.

4.3 | Model fitting and model selection

We analysed the actual dataset using the removal-distance sampling model. We used 15 years of data with complete survey effort spanning 2005–2022. We fit five candidate models for abundance: a null model (NULL), a model where abundance differed by habitat type (HAB), a model where abundance changed linearly over time (YEAR), a model where abundance differed by habitat and over time (HAB + YEAR), and a model with an interaction between habitat and time (HAB \times YEAR). All abundance models included random intercepts by point, and all detection models included only an intercept. We compared models using AIC. Code and data to replicate this analysis is available from Zenodo (Kellner et al., 2023).

4.4 | Results and discussion

Our power to detect a difference in abundance between habitat A and B (5 vs. 6 birds per point) was 0.71, and power to detect a declining trend in abundance of approximately 2% yearly was 0.81. The top-ranked model for abundance fit to the real data included effects of habitat type and year, as well as their interaction (HAB \times YEAR), on abundance (Table 4).

Based on the top-ranked model, Acadian Flycatcher abundance declined in both habitat types (Figures 1 and 2). This is consistent with range-wide declines in the species as documented by the North American Breeding Bird Survey, which indicated a 10% range-wide decline during 1970–2014 (Rosenberg et al., 2016). Acadian Flycatcher abundance in our case study was initially about 55% greater in hardwood plantation habitat relative to bottomland hardwood forest along river levees. However, abundance declined more slowly in bottomland hardwoods (about 2.7% annually) compared to hardwood plantation habitats (7.0% annually), resulting in similar estimated abundances in both habitats by the end of the survey period (Figure 2). The initial difference in abundance may relate to more favourable habitat structure for Acadian Flycatchers in the hardwood plantations at the beginning of the survey period, including ample space among plantation rows

TABLE 4 Comparison of four candidate models for abundance of Acadian Flycatcher *Empidonax vireescens* in Roanoke River National Wildlife Refuge, North Carolina, USA, 2005–2022. Models included effects of habitat type (HAB), time (YEAR), habitat and year (HAB + YEAR) and their interaction (HAB \times YEAR), and no covariates (NULL). Parameter count includes only the fixed effect parameters in each model; all models also included random intercepts by point count location.

Model	Parameters	AIC	Δ AIC
HAB \times YEAR	6	4322.14	0.00
HAB + YEAR	5	4329.85	7.71
YEAR	4	4330.65	8.52
HAB	4	4366.48	44.35
NULL	3	4367.29	45.15

that promoted a diverse and complex midstory relative to that of bottomland forests (Hazler et al., 2006; J. Richter, pers. comm., 2022). The different rates of decline between the two habitats could reflect the stability of the habitats over the survey period—the bottomland hardwood forest canopy and midstory structure had changed little whereas the dominant trees in the hardwood plantation matured, shading out and simplifying the midstory, in addition to significant hardwood thinning in 2015 (J. Richter, pers. comm, 2022).

5 | CONCLUSION

The unmarked package has been cited widely in studies of abundance and occurrence since 2010 (based on Google Scholar search, December 2022). Notable recent improvements to the package include additional models for multi-species occupancy (Rota et al., 2016), multi-state (MacKenzie et al., 2009), and multi-season data (Dail & Madsen, 2011), power analysis tools, and support for random effects. In addition to new features, we improved the quality and reliability of the underlying code, including more extensive code testing. Such improvements will be crucial for successfully maintaining and expanding unmarked over the next decade.

We plan for unmarked development to continue to keep pace with advances in hierarchical modelling in ecology. This will involve support for new data types and models, along with improved tools for diagnostics and inference. We expect to improve support for large detection datasets collected in continuous time, such as from camera trap arrays and ARUs. Such data are becoming increasingly available due to advances in camera/ARU technology and machine learning (Rhinehart et al., 2020; Tabak et al., 2019). We are also developing models that incorporate data from multiple sampling designs and/or studies (i.e. integrated models). For example, we recently added support for a combined distance sampling/removal model (Amundson et al., 2014) and are implementing a model that can integrate distance sampling, point count and detection/non-detection data (Kéry et al., 2022).

```
Call:
gdistremoval(lambdaformula = ~Habitat * Year + (1 | Point),
removalformula = ~1, distanceformula = ~1, data = umf,
output = "abund")
```

The code used to run the model

Abundance:

Random effects:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
Point	(Intercept)	0.035	0.187

Estimate of the variance (and SD) of the random intercepts in the abundance submodel

Fixed effects:

	Estimate	SE	z	P(> z)
(Intercept)	1.8360	0.08391	21.88	4.06e-106
HabitatHardwood Plantation	0.4393	0.12746	3.45	5.67e-04
Year	-0.0270	0.00773	-3.49	4.77e-04
HabitatHardwood Plantation:Year	-0.0455	0.01476	-3.08	2.07e-03

Estimates, SE, z-score and p-values of fixed effect parameters for abundance submodel

Distance:

Estimate	SE	z	P(> z)
2.81	0.0222	126	0

Estimate of parameter for the distance submodel (the intercept)

Removal:

Estimate	SE	z	P(> z)
-0.682	0.0515	-13.2	6.44e-40

Estimate of parameter for removal submodel (the intercept)

AIC: 4322.137

The model's AIC score

FIGURE 1 Coefficients from the top-ranked model of Acadian Flycatcher *Empidonax virescens* abundance from a study in Roanoke River National Wildlife Refuge, North Carolina, USA, 2005–2022. The top-ranked model included effects of habitat, year, and their interaction on abundance. The reference level for habitat type was river levee. Results are shown in the format returned by unmarked, with added annotations.

FIGURE 2 Estimated Acadian Flycatcher *Empidonax virescens* (ACFL) abundance and 95% confidence interval in two habitat types over time in Roanoke River National Wildlife Refuge, North Carolina, USA, 2005–2022 based on the top-ranked model.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Richard B. Chandler, Kenneth F. Kellner, J. Andrew Royle, Marc Kéry and Adam D. Smith contributed to the R package. Kenneth F. Kellner and Adam D. Smith wrote the first draft of the manuscript. All authors contributed significantly to the content of the manuscript.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

No conflicts of interest have been declared.

PEER REVIEW

The peer review history for this article is available at <https://www.webofscience.com/api/gateway/wos/peer-review/10.1111/2041-210X.14123>.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The unmarked package is available on CRAN (<https://cran.r-project.org/package=unmarked>). The development version of the package used in the application, and the package source code, can be found at <https://github.com/rbchan/unmarked>. The code and data for running the application are available from Zenodo (Kellner et al., 2023).

ORCID

Kenneth F. Kellner <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6755-0555>

Adam D. Smith <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4863-2395>

J. Andrew Royle <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3135-2167>

Richard B. Chandler <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4930-2790>

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

Table S1. unmarked models described in the text, along with descriptions and corresponding citations.

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